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Efficacy of some botanical oils on the control of dura andat *Agonoscelis pubescens* (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae) at Elsouky, Sennar State, Sudan

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Abstract

Dura andat, *Agonoscelis pubescens* (Thunberg) (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae), is considered as one of the national pests that infect Dura with its various varieties before the maturity of grains is reached milky stage. It causes severe economic damage in the sorghum production areas in Sudan in the rain fed and irrigated sectors. Laboratory and field experiments were conducted to evaluate the efficacy of some botanical oils, i.e., sunflower seed, sesame seed and neem seed oils, in three different concentrations (2.5, 5, 7.5 ml, in 100 ml water) and petroleum oil (2.5 ml carried in 100 ml water) against adult stage of dura andat bug adult. The laboratory experiment was conducted in the Biology Laboratory, Faculty of Agricultural Sciences, University of Gezira using complete randomized design (CRD) with four replicates and insect mortality was evaluated after 24, 48 and 72 hrs. after exposure. The study showed the great effect of botanical oils on the insect, which is represented in the large death rate with significant different between the treatments. The sunflower oil with a concentration of 2.5% and neem seed oil with a concentration of 7.5 shows highest percentage of mortality, 95%, and 90% respectively compared to untreated control which recorded the lowest mortality of 12.5%. Also, doses with great efficacy of each oil (Except petroleum oil) were evaluated by applying them in the field at Elsouky, Sennar State, and the area selected according to roosting site of the pest. Where both neem seed oil of concentration 7.5 and the insecticide (Hitcel) obtained 100% of mortality, followed by sunflower oil with a concentration of 2.5% and sesame oil 7.5% with mortality of 98.33% for each. The study indicates the possibility of using neem seed oil with concentration 7.5%, sunflower oil with concentration 2.5% and sesame seed oil with concentration 7.5% as promising alternatives to hazardous and costly synthetic chemical for management of dura andat management in Sudan.

Introduction

Dura andat *Agonoscelis pubescens* (Thunberg) (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae) is a serious pest of

sorghum. It occurs in a number of African countries, South of the Sahara (Sudan, Uganda, Kenya, Tanzania, Somalia, Zimbabwe, South Africa,

Nigeria, Ghana and Madagascar) (Schmutterer, 1969 and Kranz *et al.*, 1977). It was also reported from Kenya by Pelley and Le (1979) and from Nigeria by Adam *et al.* (1999). *A. pubescens* inhabits mainly the central rain lands belt in Sudan which lies within the isohyets 250-800 mm and is the main sorghum producing area in the country. The pest appears to breed in large numbers and exhibit its typical clustering habit during the resting period only in areas within the isohyets 350-550 mm (Razig, 1978). In the White Nile area, the distribution map of the dura andat changes with the change in sorghum production areas. Up to year 1951 the infested area was north of latitude 13° 00" N but in 1974-1975 the infested area extended to Renk (South Sudan Republic), Latitude 11° 25' and Mieginis, Latitude 12° 20' (El-Mustafa, 1975 and Fadlemula, 2003). Dura andat, a primary pest of sorghum, was also recorded on faba bean plants at El-Rahad (14° 00" N, 34° 00" E) which is one of the new areas for expansion of faba bean production in the Sudan (Kannan, 1989). In Gedarif State, where large scale rain-fed farming is practiced, *Sorghum bicolor* (L.) and *Sesame indicum* are produced in large quantities, *A. pubescens* was reported as a pest mainly of sorghum crop in that area. However, Schmutterer (1969) and Mohamed (1977) reported infestation of sunflower heads by *A. pubescens*. Razig (1978) reported that *A. pubescens* could damage 20-50% of the sorghum crop in some sorghum producing areas and, in few localities, a total loss of sorghum crop occurred. The control of both agricultural and medical insect pests in Sudan and worldwide depends mainly on the use of synthetic insecticides, but their

problems are continuously increasing. Such problems include exposure of man and animal to serious hazards, destruction of beneficial organisms in addition to their high cost. This situation has led to the search for other alternatives methods of control, particularly those of plant origin to reduce the heavy use of chemical insecticides and alleviate their hazards (Fernandez and Montagne, 1990).

The use of natural products for pests control can employ a combination of techniques which help achieve the required benefits and minimize the harmful side effects that may arise from exclusive use of synthetic pesticides. Also, botanical insecticides can break down readily in soil and environment and are not stored in plant or animal tissues. Botanical insecticides are therefore safe and can be applied by farmers and small-scale industries with little cost (Georges *et al.*, 2008). The present work aimed to study the efficacy of four botanical essential oils in controlling dura andat, *A. pubescens* at laboratory condition and field condition, heglig (*Palanites aegyptiaca*).

Materials and methods

1. Laboratory experiments:

A laboratory experiment was conducted at Biology Laboratory. Faculty of Agricultural Sciences University of Gezira during May 2019, to study the effect of some botanical oils on dura andat *A. pubescens*.

2. Collection of sorghum bug adults:

Adults of sorghum bug *A. pubescens* were collected from Alfaw area during April 2019 at the roosting stage of the insect and brought to the laboratory and maintained in cage 50/50/50 Cm and provided small

shoots of highlig *Balanites eguptiaca*. (Plate 2 c).

3. Botanical oils preparation and treatment:

Refined oils of three plants, i.e., sesame (*sesamum indicum*), sunflower (*Helianthus annus*) and neem (*Azdrachtica indica*) were obtained from Wad Madani local market. Different concentrations of 2.5 %, 5% and 7.5% from each oil were prepared by dissolving it in distilled water with final volume of 100 ml. (Plates 2 a and b). However, to make the oils suitable for application few drops of liquid soap were added to act as an emulsifier. The different botanical oil treatment was evaluated against adult of *A. pubescens* in comparison with petroleum oil and standard commercial insecticide Hitcel 44% Ec. (Profenfos 40% + cypermethrin 4%). The laboratory experiment consisted of twelve treatments as follows:

T1 = Sesame oil at the rate of 2.5% concentration.

T2 =Sesame oil at the rate of 5% concentration.

T3 = Sesame oil at the rate of 7.5% concentration.

T4 =Neem seed oil at the rate of 2.5% concentration.

T5 = Neem seed oil at the rate of 5% concentration.

T6 =Neem seed oil at the rate of 7.5% concentration.

T7 =Sunflower oil at the rate of 2.5% concentration.

T8 = Sunflower oil at the rate of 5% concentration.

T9 = Sunflower oil at the rate of 7.5% concentration,

T10 = Hitcel 44% EC (Profenfos 40%, cypermethrin 4%).

T11 = Petroleum oil 2.5 % (Pet 2.5%).

T12 = Untreated Control (UTC).

4. Botanical oils insecticidal effect bioassay:

Ten healthy adult insects and small shoots of highlig were introduced together into glass gars, the insects were sprayed by micro sprayer (1 liter) (Plate 2 d). of different botanical oils treatment and carefully closed by with mesh (Allow air entrance) to prevent insects from scape (Plate 1). The water treatment control and standard insecticide were induced for comparison. The experiment was carried out in completely randomized design (CRD) with four replicates of each treatment. The average temperature and humidity percentage were recorded (By using hygrometer) in the laboratory during the study period. The number of dead insects were observed after 24 and 48 hrs. from the time of exposure to the treatment. Mortality was confirmed by touching the insect with fine brush, insect that appeared no realistic movement were considered as dead. The percentage mortality of individuals calculated and recorded.

Plate (1): Jars with treated dura andat under laboratory conditions.

(a) Micro pipette

(b) Measuring cylinder

(c) Rearing cage

(d) Micro sprayer

Plate (2): a. Micro pipette, b. Measuring cylinder, c. Rearing.

The study was carried out during June 2019 at Elsoky, Sennar State and the area selected according to roosting site of the pest. With five treatments and three replications. Only the effective dose from each botanical oil examined in laboratory applied in this experiment i.e. (Sunflower seed oil 2.5%), (Sesame seed oil 7.5%), and (Neem seed oil 7.5% and Hitcel insecticide. The study area was big tree crowded with duranta and its branches represent the experimental units (Plate 3). Each concentration replicated three times. Twenty insects in twenty centimeters of

each branch were counted and treated with desirable concentration of selected oils and covered with piece of mosquito net to prevent insect escape from the branch (Plate 4 a, b, c and d). The mortality was observed after 72 hrs. of application

5. Statistical analysis:

The data obtained were subjected to the Analysis of Variance using (Statistic 8 software) after transformation, if needed, and the values of the grand mean, standard error and coefficient of variation were calculated. Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) was used to separate means among treatments.

Plate (3): The tree under study.

(a) Measuring the distance in branch

(b) Fixing of the nets

(c) E: treatment

(d) C3: treatment

Plate (4): Measuring the distance in branch, fixing the nets, treatments (E and C3).

Results and discussion

1. The effect of some botanical oils on *dura* andat *Agonoscelis pubescence* after 24 hrs. of treatment under laboratory conditions:

Application of the preparations of botanical suspension induced mortality on treated sorghum seed bug irrespective of the applied dose. In the different doses the mortality levels were significantly higher in eleven concentrations compared to the untreated control. Also, the morality was higher in different doses with deferent concentration. Table (1) showed the result of insect adult mortality after 24 hrs. from the treatment of botanical oils concentrations , there was significant difference between treatments. The highest mortality was recorded with sunflower seed oil (37.5%) at concentration 2.5% followed by

sunflower seed (5%) treatment (30%), while there was no significant difference between the rest of treatment including positive and negative control i.e., Hitcel and untreated control. On the other hand, comparison of mean treatment of tested botanical oils showed that the highest mortality was sunflower seed oil treatment (28.33%) compared to other means, the sunflower at 2.5% concentration showed highest mortality percentage within all treatment. (Figure 1). Followed by sesame seed oil (20.83%) (Figure 2). Which is statistically on par with positive control Hitcel (20.5%.) while sesame seed oil treatments showed lowest percentage mortality (2.5%) among the botanical oils with no mortality of 2.5% and 5% concentration, while the concentration 7.5% showed 7.5% mortality (Figure 2).

Table (1): Effect of some botanicals on *dura* andat *Agonoscelis pubescens* mortality 24 hrs. of treatment, under laboratory conditions.

Treatment	Mean percentage mortality General	Treatment Mean
Sunflower seed oil 2.5	37.500 (6.0275) a	(5.4160) 28.33 a
Sunflower seed oil 5%	30.000 (5.4675) a	
Sunflower seed oil 7.5%	17.500 (4.1975) ab	
Sesame seed oil 2.5 %	0.0000 (1.0000) b	(1.870)2.5 b
Sesame seed oil 5%	0.0000 (1.0000) b	
Sesame seed oil 7.5%	7.5000 (2.4750) ab	
Neem seed oil 2.5%	17.500 (3.4300) ab	(4.6726)20.833 a
Neem seed oil 5%	27.500 (5.1525) ab	
Neem seed oil 7.5%	17.500 (3.9325) ab	
Hitcel 44% (.25%)	20.500 (4.3125) ab	(4.6368) 20.500 a
Petroleum oil 2.5%	1.0000 (1.3525) ab	(1.4142)1.000 b
Untreated control	0.0000 (1.0000) b	(1.000)0.00 b
SE+	1.1746	.3742
CV %	49.54	20.80

Means followed by same letter(s) are not significantly different at 0.05 levels. Means in parentheses are transformed to $\sqrt{x+1}$.

Figure (1): Percentage mortality of *Agonoscelis pubescens* after 24 hrs. treated with sunflower seed oil.

Figure (2): Percentage mortality of *Agonoscelis pubescens* after 24 hrs. treated with sesame seed oil.

2. The effect of some botanical oils on *dura* andat *Agonoscelis pubescence* after 48 hrs. of treatment under laboratory condition:

Table (2) presented the percentage mortality rate of *A. pubescens* adult after forty-eight hrs. of treatment with different botanical oils concentration. The highest mortality percentage is 80% recorded from treatment of sesame oil at concentration of 7.5% followed by 72% of neem seed oil at same concentration and 70% mortality of sesame oil of 5% concentration and this statistically fall in line with all

sunflower seed oil treatment at the three concentrations. i.e., 2.5%, 5% and 7.5% with mortality of 57.5%, 62.5% and 65%, respectively. While the rest of the treatment showed statically no significant difference between them included the positive control Hitcel and negative untreated control. However, among the tested botanical oils after 48hrs. of application, sesame oil achieved highest mortality (68.83%) of treatment mean followed by sunflower and neem seed oils, treatment means mortality of 61.6% and 59.16% respectively.

Table (2): Effect of some botanicals on *dura* andat *Agonoscelis pubescens* mortality 48 hrs. of treatment, under laboratory condition.

Treatment	Mean percentage mortality General	Treatment Mean
Sunflower seed oil 2.5	57.500 (7.5875) a	(7.8825) 61.66 ab
Sunflower seed oil 5%	62.500 (7.9400) a	
Sunflower seed oil 7.5%	65.000 (8.1200) a	
Sesame seed oil 2.5 %	56.500 (7.0825) ab	(8.3566)68.83 a
Sesame seed oil 5%	70.000 (8.4175) a	
Sesame seed oil 7.5%	80.000 (8.9325) a	
Neem seed oil 2.5%	55.000 (7.3800) ab	(7.7561)59.16.5 ab
Neem seed oil 5%	50.000 (7.0000) ab	
Neem seed oil 7.5%	72.500 (8.5250) a	
Hitcel 44% (.25%)	52.500 (7.2375) ab	(7.3143) 52.500 b
Petroleum oil 2.5%	57.500 (7.3950) ab	(7.6485)57.5 ab
Untreated control	12.500 (3.3700) b	(3.6742)12.5 c
SE+	1.0975	.2501
CV %	20.93	6.10

Means followed by same letter(s) are not significantly different at 0.05 levels. Means in parentheses are transformed to $\sqrt{x+1}$

3. Efficiency of some botanical oils to control *dura* andat *Agonoscelis pubescens*:

The result of effect of different botanical oils was presented in Table (3), showed that highest mortality percentage recorded from sunflower seed oil at 2.5% concentration (95%), followed by 5% concentration of the same treatment (92%) then neem seed oil which sustained (90%) at 7.5% concentration, while the untreated control showed the lowest mortality percentage (12.5%), however; the rest of the treatments statistically on par with positive control Hitcel. On the other hand, sunflower oil treatment showed highest mortality

percentage (90%). The mortality percentage decreased with concentration increase (Figures 3 and 4). Followed by neem seed oil treatment, the mortality percentage (80%) increases mortality with increase in concentration. (Figures 3 and 5). Generally, the botanical seed oils of tested three plants with different concentration showed mortality of *A. pubescens* adults after 24 and 48hrs. of treatments. The sunflower seed oil at 2.5% concentration performed better, while the sesame and neem seed oil at 7.5% concentration performed better compared to the others and these treatments were selected for field experiments to confirm their efficacy.

Table (3): Efficacy of some botanical oils to control *dura* andat *Agonoscelis pubescens*.

Treatment	Mean percentage mortality General	Treatment Mean
Sunflower seed oil 2.5	95 (13.615) a	90 a
Sunflower seed oil 5%	92.5 (13.408) a	
Sunflower seed oil 7.5%	82.5 (12.313) ab	
Sesame seed oil 2.5 %	70 (8.082) bc	75.83 bc
Sesame seed oil 5%	70 (9.418) ab	
Sesame seed oil 7.5%	87.5 (11.408) ab	
Neem seed oil 2.5%	72.5 (10.810) ab	80 ab
Neem seed oil 5%	77.5 (12.148) ab	
Neem seed oil 7.5%	90 (12.455) a	
Hitcel 44% (0.25%)	73 (11.548) ab	73 bc
Petroleum oil 2.5%	67.5 (9.640) ab	67.5 c
Untreated control	12.5 (4.370) c	12 d
SE+	1.1734	3.551
CV %	15.41	9.26

Means followed by same letter(s) are not significantly different at 0.05 levels. Means in parentheses are transformed to $\sqrt{x+1}$.

Figure (3): Percentage mortality of *Agonoscelis pubescens* after 24 hrs. treated with neem seed oil.

Figure (4): Percentage mortality of *Agonoscelis pubescens* after 24 hrs. treated with petroleum oil.

Figure (5): Percentage mortality of *Agonoscelis pubescens* after 48 hrs. treated with sunflower seed oil.

4. The mortality of *Agonoscelis pubescens* adults treated with different neem, sesame and sunflower seed oils under field conditions:

All treatments were induced effect on treated dura and dat with respect of the concentration (Table 4) and Figure (6). All effective doses examined in laboratory gave highly significant difference with control when applied at the field. From the data presented, the

result showed that there was highly significant difference between treatments. Hitcel 44% (.25%) and neem seed oil 7.5% reported mortality (100%) which is statistically on par with sunflower seed oil at 2.5% concentration and sesame seed oil at 7.5% concentration with mortality percentage of 98.33%. On the other hand, untreated control showed lowest percentage mortality (6.67%).

Table (4): The mortality of *Agonoscelis pubescens* adults after 72 hrs. of treatment with neem, sesame and sunflower seed oils under field conditions.

Treatment	Mean percentage mortality 72 hrs.
Sunflower seed oil (2.5)	98.33 a
Sesame seed oil (7.5%)	98.33 a
Neem seed oil (7.5%)	100.00 a
Hitcel 44% (0.25%)	100.00 a
Untreated control	6.67 b
SE+	1.9720
CV %	2.99

Means followed by same letter(s) are not significantly different at 0.05 levels.

Figure (6): Percentage mortality of *Agonoscelis pubescens* after 48 hrs. treated with sesame seed oil.

Direct application of botanical oils on dura andat *A. pubescens* at the resting period at the field and laboratory caused high mortality. The oils was found to be highly effect on *A. pubescens* where 80% mortality was obtained after 48 hrs. after application at laboratory , in addition to 100% mortality was obtained after 72 hrs. after application in field .according to Mustafa (2004) The high mortality observed in adult dura andat *A. pubescens* might be due to the following reasons: (i the weak physiological situation of the pest, (ii the high temperature which more increased in the body of pest by the addition of oils, (iii the hyperactivity of the pest as result of outer stimulation which is the oil suspension, that can lead to breaking of resting period and more consuming of energy, (iv little stored fats at the end of the previous season,). The above reasons may help explain the high mortality of *A. pubescens* within short time period (80% and 100% mortality after 2 and 3 days in lab and field, respectively). It should also increase the search for more botanical oils that can be used for the control of the economically important pests. The results obtained in this study, indicate that most of the doses used were lethal to the pest. There is no doubt that all treatments were effective against dura andat *A. pubescens* especially Hitcel 44%, neem seed oil 7.5, sesame oil 7.5 and sunflower 2.5. These treatments were the effective doses obtained from laboratory experiments and field. Wessal *et al.* (2019) reported that sesame oil was found to be more effective in controlling the onion thrips. The same result obtained experiments at laboratory, and it found that it was more affabulatory, neem seed 7.5 and Hitcel at field experiment. Elamin (1955) reported that sesame seed oil (Refined) at 2- 3 % as oil water emulsion + agral

(or liquid soap) led to significant decrease in TYLCV and significant increase in yield. Also, Wessal *et al.* (2019) reported that sunflower seed oil came at the fifth degree of effectiveness after sesame oil, groundnut, petroleum oil, and cotton oil, this result is similar to our present result for the second day laboratory result of sunflower which came at the fourth degree of effectiveness after sesame 7.5%, neem seed 7.5%, and sesame 5 %. But laboratory experiments showed that sunflower 2.5 and neem seed oil (7.5%) were the effective doses followed by the insecticide Hitcel and sesame seed oil (7.5%). Singh *et al.* (2012) reported that some oils such as those derived from neem, karanja (*Pongamia glabra*), undi (*Calophyllum inophyllum*) and kusum (*Schleichera triguga*) also have an insecticidal effect, and a small amount may kill about 90 % of the Cowpea weevil (*Callosobruchus maculatus*). Onu and Ikehi (2015) reported that a mixture of both extracts (neem, garlic and neem-garlic mixture) was the most effective control for the storage pests of maize, rice and beans with death record of 100% for *Sitophilus zeae*. And *Sitophilus oryzae* and 95% for *Callosobruchus maculatus*. Within 5 treatment days. The treated grains were found to be safe for consumption. In our present study the neem seed oil (7.5%) was found to be very effective against dura andat *A. pubescens* in both lap and field which recorded the highest effect at lab after sunflower oil 2.5 and recorded highest effect in field as the same as the insecticide Hitcel 44%. Both neem seed oil (7.5%) and the insecticide Hitcel 44% were found to be sustained high mortality in field which reach 100% followed by sunflower seed oil (%2.5%) and sesame oil (7.5%) which reach 98.33%. Therefore, further studies are needed to characterize the active compound in the tested botanical oils that have insecticidal properties for

recommending for IPM programs against dura andat and other insect pests.

This study clearly demonstrates the effectiveness of the botanical oils i.e. sunflower seed oil, sesame seed oil, neem seed oil and petroleum oil for the control of dura andat *A. pubescens* under laboratory and field condition. From the result obtained it is concluded that: There is no considerable variation between the insecticide Hitcel 44%, and most botanical seed oils used for controlling dura andat (*A. pubescens*) Hitcel 44% and neem seed oil demonstrated an excellent performed in dura andat control in the field. The sunflower oil treatment with low concentration was the best among the tested botanical seed oils in controlling of *A. pubescens* at the laboratory after short time of application (48 hrs.). The neem seed oil 7.5% concentration showed 100% of mortality as the same as insecticide Hitcel at field experiment after short time. From the result obtained it is noticed that botanical oils can control the pest in relatively short time (Three days). So it is suggested that the chemical insecticide can be replaced by neem seed oil 7.5, sunflower seed oil 2.5 and sesame oil 7.5 or use one of these oils and supplemented by Hitcel 44% (0.25%) with low dose when the weather condition is suitable. The culture of using more safety materials to control agricultural pests should be disseminated to reduce the hazardous cost and the developing of resistance by the pest to chemical insecticides.

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